

Review of the Extraction vs. Non-Extraction Debate

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Abstract

Orthodontics boasts a rich history intertwined with controversies that seem to persist indefinitely, unlike disputes, due to their inability to be conclusively resolved through scientific evidence alone. One of these enduring controversies revolves around the choice between extraction and non-extraction treatment modalities. There has been a noticeable decline in the use of extraction in orthodontic care, partly driven by increased pressure from referring dentists to opt for non-extraction approaches, often without full awareness of the supporting literature for extractions in specific cases over the past two decade. This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview, including the historical background of the controversy, perspectives from various authors, the reasons behind the decline in extraction cases, and the current state of understanding regarding this ongoing debate .

Introduction

From the perspective of the layperson, malocclusion is more commonly associated with crowding than with spacing issues. Addressing a crowded dental arch typically involves creating space, which can be accomplished through either extraction or non-extraction methods. The concept of extracting teeth to make room for the remaining crowded teeth dates back to at least 1771 and was considered innovative at the time, though it is now a well-established practice.

History

Since the dawn of civilization, deciduous tooth extraction has been a common procedure. When Celsus and Pierre Fauchard proposed the extraction of deciduous teeth to make room for permanent successors, there was little to no resistance (Hunter et al 1865)¹. When dentists began extracting permanent teeth in order to undergo the procedure, disagreements emerged. The leading author, Hunter (Natural History of Teeth, 1771), was against it because he believed it to be a development inhibitor. Class II division 1 malocclusions were typically treated in the early 1800s by extracting the maxillary first premolars. However, Delabarre cautioned against its unfavorable consequences in 1818² (Brodie et al 1934). "Teeth extractions are much easier to do than

determining whether they are absolutely necessary," he remarked. Davenport, Isaac B. (1887)². gave a speech in opposition to extractions in New York, claiming that the procedure resulted in "A loss of an important organ." (Davenport et al 1887)³

The most important, energetic, and powerful person in orthodontics was Edward H. Angle. As the "Father of Modern Orthodontics," he is revered. (Wahl et al)⁴ At first, Edward Hartley Angle thought that the only way to address orthodontic treatment issues was to extract teeth. The sixth edition of Angle's book, "Treatment of Malocclusion of the Teeth and Fractures of the Maxillae-Angle System," was released in 1900 and included a tonne of information and case studies on tooth extractions. Angle promoted extraction as a way to enhance face⁵ (Angel EH 1903)

The Extraction Debate

Angle's theories were not without opposition. Calvin Case, his fiercest professional adversary, contended that most patients would not find the stability and esthetics adequate in the long run, even if the arches were stretched to align all of the teeth (Wahl N 1988)⁶. Martin Dewey, an Angle student, and Calvin Case engaged in a highly public-

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ized argument as the controversy's climax. This struggle began in 1911 and resulted in "The Extraction Debate of 1911." During a 1911 National Dental Association meeting in an article titled "The Question of Extraction in Orthodontia," Association member Calvin Case expressed his strong disagreement with the creationist beliefs of the Angle School, citing their ignorance of heredity as a cause of malocclusion and their belief that malocclusion was caused by local factors and that correcting teeth in their intended positions would produce a harmonious facial structure. (Wahl N, C, Busch LS 2014)^{4,7}

Reasons For Controversy

Facial Profile: When selecting between extraction and non-extraction therapy modalities, the patient's soft tissue profile is the primary consideration. (Rushing SE, Stephens CK, Erdinc AE 2007)¹²⁻¹⁴ Some people disagree with extractions, arguing that they "dish in" the face. On the other hand, extractionists assert that in some situations, not getting extractions will worsen periodontal health and make the profile look fuller. The inability of general dentists and orthodontists to differentiate between the facial profiles of patients treated with extraction and those treated without it is supported by studies done by Rushing et al in 1995, Stephens et al in 2005, and Erdinc et al in 2007. (Rushing SE, Stephens CK, Erdinc AE 2007)¹²⁻¹⁴

Extractions & Temporomandibular Joint Disorders (TMD): In 1987, a groundbreaking district court case concerned a sixteen-year-old girl who had been diagnosed with division 1 malocclusion, or Angle's Class II. Her orthodontist designed the course of therapy, which included headgear and premolar extractions. Her family then sued the orthodontist, claiming that the procedure was the cause of her TMD. Their family dentist argued that the usage of headgear and extractions led to internal derangement and excessive incisor retraction as a result of the mandible's distal displacement. The jury found the orthodontist guilty of mistreating patients, and dental professionals discussed the matter extensively. The majority of orthodontists did not think that premolar extractions could cause TMD, but if they recommended extraction therapy, their risk of being sued for malpractice increased. The orthodontic scientific community took the lead in the early 1990s and presented strong evidence that orthodontic therapy and TMD are not causally related. The idea that all orthodontic treatments have a neutral impact is also covered and supported by the literature. (Gianelly AA, Brodie AG)^{21,2}

Reasons for Decline in Extractions

Bonding: More patients were able to have non-extraction therapy thanks to the bonding of fixed appliances, which largely replaced banding because band thicknesses tended to encourage crowding.

Expansion: Expansion has been promoted since long to treat posterior crossbite. In the 1980s, it became popular as a substitute to extraction treatment to resolve crowding even without the presence of posterior crossbite. Advocates of rapid maxillary expansion (RME) claim resolving of borderline crowding of 3-6mm in the mandible in patients with narrow transpalatal

widths. They contend that RME will result in reciprocal mandibular expansion because the mandibular arch form is dictated by the maxillary arch form. McNamara Jr. et al reported that a favourable change in the sagittal occlusal relationships between maxillary and mandibular teeth can be facilitated by RME. Fields cautioned that "to date, there is no credible long-term post retention evidence that early intervention to prepare, develop, balance, or expand arches by any other name has any efficacy in providing a less crowded permanent dentition later". (McNamara Jr JA 2010)³²

Stability of expansion, particularly in the mandible, has little evidence demonstrating the same. Many authors support the contention that intercanine expansion is unstable. A study by Housley et al in 2003 concluded that in patients who underwent mandibular expansion, intercanine widths were maintained in only 8% of patients, for six years and three months after fixed retention. (Housley et al 2003)³³ Additionally, prospective complications of expansion include the risks of creating a dehiscence (loss of alveolar bone on the facial aspect of a tooth that leaves a characteristic oval, root-exposed defect from the cemento-enamel junction apically) as a result of over-expansion. (Fig. 8). Anterior teeth tend to move labially, when treated by expansion of the arches to alleviate moderate to severe crowding. Extractions on the other hand, allow the teeth to move along the alveolus. (Fields Jr et al 2013)³⁴

Conclusions

Identifying guidelines for the extraction vs non-extraction decision in orthodontic treatment is a complex task. Presently, the controversy is not afflicted by as much beliefs as it was almost 100 years ago and both treatment options are still open. The option to treat with extraction or non-extraction should be made objectively for each case based on strong evidence with equal attention on the soft tissue paradigm.

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